

Speculation on Electromagnetic Work as Part Mass Energy and Part Field Rearrangement Energy

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In special relativity, energy is equated with mass through $E=mc^2$. For example, two identical particles with the same kinetic energy (part of mass energy), joined by a spring, may convert this kinetic energy into potential energy as they approach and finally touch (and are fastened). Then the potential energy appears as rest mass energy in addition to the rest masses of the particles.

One might consider a similar approach to assembling charges on a conductor or building a sphere of charge. In such a case, kinetic energy is converted into potential energy because work is done. This work, however, is considered from the point of view of the central charge, i.e. $q \phi(r)$ is the energy of a charge q being brought in (at r). Each q has its own electric field which is added to the core field when it arrives and is "attached". In addition, the potential field changes as well. As one brings in various q pieces, they add to E/ϕ based on their attachment position, but their self energies do not add because it is the total E which is used in $\int \epsilon_0 E \cdot E$. As a result, the scenario differs from the two masses joined by a spring. In (1), we suggested that work may be converted into different energy forms other than simply that of mass. We suggest that there is energy in the rearrangement of the electrostatic potential field in assembling a charge Q . This energy manifests itself in the potential which yields an energy of $q_1 \phi(r)$ for a test charge q_1 .

We try to apply this idea to an accelerating charge in the case of a small (nonrelativistic) v ($v/c \ll 1$). We find that the usual em $\int \epsilon_0 E(v) \cdot E(v) + \int \mu_0 B(v) \cdot B(v)$ term, contains usual $E(v \text{ constant}) \cdot E(v \text{ constant term})$, another proportional to $dv/dt \cdot dv/dt$ which seems to be associated with radiating photons and finally a term proportional to $v \cdot dv/dt$. This last term disappears when $dv/dt=0$ which begs the question: Where does this energy go? We suggest that if some of the em work-energy may be associated with field rearrangement, then one does not necessarily need to look for energy in the form of mass. It may be assigned to changes in the fields which is manifested in their interaction with a test charge.

Energy and Mass

The $E=Mc^2$ energy mass relationship of special relativity is well-known. Kinetic energy represents part of mass energy from $m_0 c^2 / \sqrt{1-v^2/c^2}$, where m_0 is rest mass, and if it is converted into potential energy, this should also be considered part of mass.

It is possible, however, that one has nonadditive energy situations linked with force fields and the creation of new overall fields. In such a case, it seems that one cannot immediately associate work-energy with mass.

A specific example involves a charge at rest. Its self-energy is $\int \epsilon_0 E \cdot E$, but there is a second energy in the problem, namely $q_1 \phi(r)$ where q_1 is a test charge and ϕ the electrostatic potential of the source charge Q . It is interesting that this potential energy may be written solely in terms of the source potential (as if the field and self-energy of the test charge do not matter). They, however, do matter and so one does not have the simple case of converting

kinetic energy of q_1 into potential energy as one tries to create a large charge $Q+q_1$. A new E field and potential are created depending at which r point q_1 is attached. Even though the rest mass of q_1 is additive, its self-energy is not. One calculates an overall E (which is directly related to force through $F = q E$, electrostatic case). This in turn is linked to an energy $q_{test} \phi$ new which transforms as the fourth component of 4-vector. Overall the field of the system is changed and we argue that some of the work-energy, $.5 \epsilon_0 E \cdot E$, is associated with this change and manifested in $q_{test} \phi$ new and not just in an increased rest mass of the system.

In (1), we argue that this explains why:

$$.5 \epsilon_0 E \cdot E \text{ doesn't } \rightarrow (.5 \epsilon_0 E \cdot E) / \sqrt{1-vv/cc} \quad ((1))$$

In this note, we try to apply this idea of work-energy to an accelerating charge. In particular, we argue that pieces of energy: $.5 \epsilon_0 E \cdot E + .5/\mu_0 B \cdot B$ do not necessarily need to manifest themselves as a kind of mass energy as they may be associated with field rearrangement.

Accelerating Charge

From (2), the E and B fields of a charge moving at constant v are:

$$E(r,t) = q/(4\pi \epsilon_0) R / (R^* R^* R^*) (1-vv/cc) \quad ((2a))$$

$$B = 1/cc \ v \times E \quad ((2b))$$

R is the vector from the charge to the measurement point.

$R^* = \sqrt{(x-x_0)^2 + b^2 (1-vv/cc)}$ where the charge moves along x and b is the y coordinate.

The fields of an accelerating charge are (2):

$$E = q/(4\pi \epsilon_0) \left\{ \frac{1}{R^* R^* R^*} [R' - |R'|v'/c](1-vv/cc) + \frac{(R' - |R'|v'/c)(dv'/dt \cdot R')}{R^* R^* R^* cc} - \frac{dv'/dt |R'|}{R^* R^* cc} \right\} \quad ((3a))$$

$$B = q/(4\pi \epsilon_0 cc) \left\{ v' \times R' / (R^* R^* R^*) (1-vv/cc) + \frac{1}{R^* R^* R^* c} R' / R \times [(R' - |R'|v'/c) \times dv'/dt] \right\} \quad ((3b))$$

Here: $R^* = R' - R' \cdot v/c$ which is the same definition as for ((2a)). ((4))

Note, v' and dv'/dt mean that r is evaluated at the retarded time.

First, one may check that for $dv'/dt=0$, ((3a)) and ((3b)) become ((2a)) and ((2b)). For example, for $dv'/dt=0$, one sees that $B = v \times \{ R' - |R'|v'/c \} / (R^* R^* R^*) (1-vv/cc)$.

Thus, one must show that $R = R' - |R'|v/c$ where R' is the vector from the retarded time position of the charge to the measurement point. If v is in the x -direction, as it is in this example, then:

R' and R have the same y component b , one needs only the x component.

$|R'|/c$ is the time for a signal (moving at c) from the retarded point to reach the measurement point. Thus: $x' - x = v |R'|/c$ and so $x' - v|R'|/c = x$ and R and $R' - |R'|v/c$ are equivalent.

For small velocities (2) gives:

$$E = q/(4\pi\epsilon_0) \left\{ E(v \text{ constant}) + 1/(R^* R^* R^*) (1/c^2) R \times [(R' - |R'|v/c) \times dv'/dt] \right\} \quad ((5a))$$

$$B = R' \times E / (|R'| c) \quad ((5b)) \quad (\text{We will ultimately ignore } B. \text{ This form is really for a radiation calculation.})$$

We wish to calculate:

$\int .5 \epsilon_0 E \cdot E + .5/\mu_0 B \cdot B$ for an accelerating charge in the $v/c \ll 1$ limit as well. Considering only $E \cdot E$ will suffice for our arguments.

For v' and dv'/dt in the same direction: (we set $c=1$)

$$E = E(\text{constant } v) + (R' \times (R' \times dv'/dt)) / (R^* R^* R^*) = E(\text{constant } v) + N \quad ((6))$$

Thus: $E \cdot E = E(v \text{ constant}) \cdot E(v \text{ constant}) + \text{term proportional to } dv'/dt \cdot dv'/dt$

$$+ 2E(v \text{ constant}) \cdot N \quad ((7))$$

One may note that $v \cdot [R' \times (R' \times dv'/dt)] = v_i \epsilon_{ijk} R'_j \epsilon_{klm} R'_l v'_m = (\delta_{il} \delta_{jm} - \delta_{im} \delta_{jl}) v'_i R'_j R'_l v'_m$

$$= dv'/dt \cdot R' \cdot v' \cdot R' - dv'/dt \cdot v' \cdot R' \cdot R' \quad ((8))$$

(Note replacing v' with R' gives 0, so the R' piece of $E(v \text{ constant})$ yields 0).

Consider motion and acceleration in one and the same direction. At this point, for convenience we call this direction z (we earlier called it x). Then:

$$((8)) = dv'/dt \cdot v' (z z - z z - b b) = dv'/dt \cdot v' b b \text{ which is nonzero and the integral of it divided by } R^* R^* R^* \text{ is also nonzero.}$$

Thus, there are three pieces of self-energy (from $E \cdot E$) ($B \cdot B$ should not change this conclusion):

((A)) $E(v \text{ constant}) \cdot E(v \text{ constant})$ - This is the usual self-energy of a constant moving charge. It represents some mass energy and some field rearrangement energy which is already present in the electrostatic case.

((B)) There is an energy piece proportional to $dv'/dt \cdot dv'/dt$ which seems to be linked to the radiation of photons whose power goes as $dv'/dt \cdot dv'/dt$. Note that in this case one has for the E piece used in $E \cdot E$, $R' \cdot R'$ type terms in the numerator and $R^* \cdot R^* \cdot R^*$ in the denominator so the drop-off is slower than usual by a power of R . Thus, one has a $1/(R^3)$ drop-off linked with radiation.

((C)) The last term is proportional to $v' \cdot dv'/dt$. If acceleration stops, this energy seems to vanish which is confusing if one expects energy to manifest itself as mass. If energy, however, may be associated with field rearrangement, which we argue is already the case for $\frac{1}{2} \epsilon_0 E \cdot E$, then this term not linked to radiation, may be associated with the change from $E(v \text{ constant})$ to $E(v+dv \text{ constant})$ which requires a field change. In other words, this energy is manifested in the new electrostatic potential at $v+dv$ and the new magnetic vector potential at $v+dv$.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that already at the level of a charge at rest, $\frac{1}{2} \epsilon_0 E \cdot E$, which is the work assembling the charge, one has some mass energy and some field rearrangement energy because each little q_1 piece brought in to create Q has its own field and self-energy. The new field is characterized by a new ϕ which is linked to an energy $q \text{ test } \phi$. Thus, self-energy may be associated with mass energy and field rearrangement energy, we argue.

We apply this idea to an accelerating charge and for $v/c \ll 1$, we find that $E \cdot E$ yields three terms. The first is proportional to $E(v \text{ constant}) \cdot E(v \text{ constant})$, the second to $dv'/dt \cdot dv'/dt$ i.e. a radiation of photons terms and the third term to: $v' \cdot dv'/dt$ (for v' and dv'/dt in the same direction). This is an unusual term because it vanishes for $dv'/dt=0$. If one only thinks in terms of energy as mass, then mass should not disappear if acceleration stops. If, however, this term represents an energy of field rearrangement, then it is manifested in $E(v+dv) \cdot E(v+dv)$ and the new potential. In other words, it shows that energy is required to rearrange $E(v)$, we argue.

References

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